

Seed technology

Influence of alkalinity on rice germination and growth

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We studied germination and seedling growth of six rice varieties at different pH levels. Tap water was used as the medium, with a pH of 7.0 and an EC of 1.0. Potassium hydroxide and acetic acid were used to adjust solution pH to 6.5, 7.5, 8.5, 9.5, and 10.5.

We placed 10 seeds of a variety in a petri dish, replicating each variety three times. Water volume was kept constant in each dish by adding solution. Germinated seeds were counted after 6 d. Seedling height and root length were measured at 6 and 10 d after transplanting (DT) (see table).

Overall germination ranged from 86 to 100% at all pH levels. Maximum germination for all varieties occurred at pH 8.5-9.5. HKR120 had the tallest seedlings at 6 DT. Seedling height,

Effect of alkalinity on growth of rice seedlings.

Variety	pH at 6 DT ^a						pH at 10 DT					
	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	Mean	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	Mean
<i>Seedling height (cm)</i>												
Jaya	2.9	2.5	2.6	2.7	1.8	2.5	4.4	4.6	4.2	3.2	2.3	3.8
PR103	3.7	3.9	3.2	2.4	1.7	3.0	4.1	4.5	5.9	3.1	2.1	3.9
HKR120	3.2	4.8	3.9	3.3	1.8	3.4	4.2	4.7	5.4	3.3	1.9	3.9
PR106	3.1	3.3	2.9	2.6	2.8	2.9	4.2	4.4	4.5	3.2	3.6	3.9
PR109	2.4	3.1	2.6	2.4	1.7	2.4	3.4	4.3	4.4	2.9	2.5	3.5
Pal 579	3.3	3.0	3.1	3.6	2.0	3.0	3.9	4.2	4.6	4.0	2.5	3.9
Mean	3.1	3.4	3.1	2.8	1.2		4.0	4.5	4.8	3.3	2.5	
LSD (0.05)	V = 0.03, pH = 0.02, V × pH = 0.15						V = ns, ^b pH = 0.13, V × pH = ns					
<i>Root length (cm)</i>												
Jaya	2.6	2.6	2.4	3.1	1.8	2.5	3.5	3.6	3.2	2.6	1.6	2.2
PR103	4.9	6.1	4.7	2.1	1.4	3.8	5.2	6.6	5.6	1.9	1.4	3.1
HKR120	2.4	4.0	2.9	2.7	1.5	2.7	2.9	4.5	4.5	2.1	1.3	3.0
PR106	3.4	4.7	4.0	3.7	3.8	3.9	3.6	3.8	4.0	3.1	3.3	3.6
PR109	3.7	4.0	3.1	2.9	2.1	3.2	3.2	3.6	3.8	3.8	1.7	3.0
Pal 579	3.8	3.0	5.3	4.8	2.0	4.0	3.4	3.5	4.1	3.9	1.8	3.3
Mean	3.5	4.2	3.7	3.2	2.1		3.6	4.3	4.2	2.7	1.8	
LSD (0.05)	V = 0.01, pH = 0.10, V × pH = 0.65						V = 0.11, pH = 0.09, V × pH = 0.57					

^aDT = days after transplanting. ^bns = not significant.

however, was not significantly different among varieties at 10 DT. Seedlings were tallest at pH 7.5 at 6 DT and at pH 8.5 at

10 DT. Pal 579 had the longest roots at 6 DT and PR106 at 10 DT; Jaya had the shortest. Roots were longest at pH 7.5. ■

Crop and resource management

Soils

Effect of green manures on ammonia-release pattern in rice soils

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We conducted an incubation study on a submerged clay loam (Vertic Ustropepts) and sandy loam (Typic Haplustalf) with green manure (GM) incorporation. Ipomoea (*Ipomoea cornea*), water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*), gliricidia (*Gliricidia sepium*), dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*), neem (*Azadirachta indica*), and calotrophis (*Calotrophis gigantea*) were incorporated at 12.5 t/ha fresh weight. Water level was maintained

at 5 ± 1 cm to keep soil submerged. We monitored ammonia-release pattern from the soils at 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 30, and 45 d after incorporation (DAI).

In the clay loam, peak NH₄⁺-N concentration was observed after 30 DAI for ipomoea and water hyacinth; the highest concentration was at 20 DAI for the other GMs. In the sandy loam, NH₄⁺-N concentration for all GMs increased progressively up to 20 DAI, after which it declined (see figure). This difference between soils could be related to their pattern degradation and minerali

N mineralization of green manures. (a) Ipomoea/water hyacinth. (b) Neem/gliciridia/calotrophis.